

IBN MANDA (310/922-395/1005)

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Annotation: This article talks about Ibn Manda, a muḥaddith, mufassir, mutakallim, historian, who has a special place in the science of ḥadīth. An attempt has been made to reveal his life and place in the science of ḥadīth. Information is also given about the teacher, student and his works.

Key words: Ḥadīth, Muḥaddith, isnād, sanad, musnad, tawḥīd.

In the process of studying the history of the science of Ḥadīth, it can be seen that the muḥaddith who lived after the third and fourth centuries of the Hijri wrote their works by interpreting, summarizing, rearranging the works of their predecessors, combining them with other works in a new way, and using other methods. At the same time, the scholars who lived in the later periods were also engaged in narrating the works of previous scholars to their students.

Ibn Manda is a scholar who left a mark in the history of Islām with his important works and narrated the works of his predecessor. The full name of the scholar is Abū ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad bin Ishāq ibn Muḥammad ibn Yaḥyā ibn Ibrahim ibn Walīd ibn Manda ibn Butta ibn Ustandār ibn D̲jahārbuk̲ht, known as Ibn Manda. The scientist was born in 310/922 in the city of Eṣfahān in present-day Iran. He is a scholar, jurist, historian and scholar. Imam Dhahabī and Imam Suyūṭī mentioned that this scholar is in the tenth class of scholars.

The scientist's father, Abū Ya‘qūb Ishāq ibn Muḥammad ibn Yaḥyā ibn Manda, was also one of the famous scholars in Eṣfahān. Therefore, Ibn Manda grew up in a scientific environment with the help of his father from his youth, and love for Sunnah appeared early in his heart. He started learning at the age of 8 after memorizing the Holy Quran. At the same time, he began to hear ḥadīth. His father paid attention to his participation in scientific meetings.

Eṣfahān was known for its scholars at that time. After Ibn Manda studied with teachers in Eṣfahān, he studied with Abū Ḥāmid ibn Bilal, Muḥammad ibn Ḥusayn Qattan, Abū ‘Abbās Asam and others in Neyshābūr. He also went to Iraq, Syria, Egypt, Mecca, Medina, Bait al-Maqdis, Sarakhs, Merv, Tripoli, Tunisia, Gaza, Caesarea, Beirut.

Ibn Manda visited many cities in search of knowledge. He first started his scientific trips by going to Neyshābūr at the age of 19. Sources say that he heard 500,000 ḥadīths there. Regarding his travels, Imam Dhahabī said: "Ibn Manda heard ḥadīths from many people during his travels. "I have never seen a person who has traveled as much as him." Another scholar, Abū Bakr Aḥmad Batirqani, quotes him as saying: "I have traveled around the East and the West twice."

The number of teachers of muḥaddith reaches 1700. Narrated by ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn Abū Hatam, Abū Abbas ibn Aqda, Fazl ibn Khasib with permission. Among his teachers were Haysama ibn Sulaiman, Haytham ibn Kulayb Shashi, Abū Aḥmad Muḥammad ibn Ibrahim Isfahani, Abū ‘Abdullāh Muḥammad ibn Ya‘qūb ibn Yusuf Shaybānī, Abū ‘Alī Ismā‘īl ibn Muhammad, Ismā‘īl ibn Ya‘qūb al-Baghdadi, Muḥammad ibn Ibrahim ibn Marwān, Muḥammad ibn Muḥammad ibn Yūnus Abhari , Hisan ibn Muḥammad Shāfi‘ī, Yaḥyā ibn ‘Abdullāh ibn Harith Dimashqi, Aḥmad ibn Sulaiman ibn Ayyub and other scholars.

Among Ibn Manda's students, there are many scholars who have reached the level of prominent imams. Even his teachers, who were higher in age and sanad than him, narrated Ḥadīth. According to muḥaddith, Taman ibn Muḥammad Rāzī, Aḥmad ibn ‘Umar, Ziyād ibn Muḥammad, his sons ‘Abd al-Raḥmān ibn Manda, Abū ‘Amr Abduwahhab ibn Manda, Ubaidullah ibn Manda, Ishāq ibn Manda, Hamza ibn Yusuf, Aḥmad ibn Fazl, Abū Sa‘īd Idrisi, Aḥmad ibn Fazl.

Many scholars have praised Ibn Manda. For example, Imam Dhahabī said: "When Abū Nu‘aym was told about Ibn Manda, he said: 'He was one of the mountains.'

Sheikh Hirat Abū Ismā‘īl Ansari said: "Abū ‘Abdullāh ibn Manda is one of the greats of his time."

Imam Jāfar ibn Muḥammad Mustaghfiri said: "I have not seen a person with a stronger memory than Abū ‘Abdullāh ibn Manda." When I asked him about the number of his teachers, he said 5,000.

Imam Dhahabī said: "There was no one who narrated more ḥadīths than him in his memory and among the reliable people."

Ibn Manda's son Abū al-Qāsim ‘Abd al-Raḥmān says that his father recorded four thousand volume, one thousand volume from Abū Sa‘īd ibn Arabi in Makkah, one thousand volume from Haisama ibn Sulayman in Taroblus, one thousand volume from A‘tham in Nishapur, and one thousand volume from Haitham ibn Kulayb (Shashi) in Bukhara.

According to Ibn Manda's ḥadīth science, " Ma'rifat al-sahāba ", "Fath al-bab fi-l-kuna wa-l-alqab", "Tasmiya al-mashoyikh", "al-Asami wa-l-kuna", "Kitāb al-kuna", "al-Naqd li musnad Abi Hanifa", "at- Tārīkh ", " Kitāb al- ṣifāt ", "Kitāb fi-n-nafs wa-r-ruh", "al-Iman", " There are works such as Kitāb at-Tawhīd.

Muḥaddith died in Eṣfahān in 395/1005.

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